

INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCES OF TEACHING SPECIAL SUBJECTS BASED ON EXPERIMENTAL APPROACHES IN LEGAL TECHNICAL COLLEGES

Pulatov Biktamish Johonovich

Independent researcher at the Institute for
Professional Education Development

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Abstract. The implementation of international experiences in teaching specialized subjects is considered one of the important directions for developing the education system and adapting it to advanced global standards. In the context of globalization and rapidly developing technologies, it is possible to increase the effectiveness of the educational process and prepare students for modern professional requirements by enriching the national education system with international experiences. This article highlights the current issues of teaching specialized subjects in vocational education based on experimental approaches.

Keywords: Special subjects, experimental approaches, international experiences, education system, pedagogy, professional preparation, practical skills, innovative methods, globalization, educational effectiveness.

The implementation of international practices in teaching specialized subjects is one of the crucial directions for developing the education system and aligning it with advanced global standards. In the context of today's globalization processes and rapidly evolving technologies, enriching the national education system with international experiences creates opportunities to enhance the effectiveness of the educational process, prepare students for modern professional requirements, and make them competitive in the international labor market.

Our initial research has shown that teaching specialized subjects in law colleges using experimental approaches not only increases students' opportunities to acquire knowledge but also enhances their ability to become proficient professionals in their field. It positively impacts the development of their independent work skills and the level of practical skills acquisition. Additionally, teaching specialized subjects based on experimental approaches in vocational education is currently one of the most pressing issues. In the present era of rapid scientific advancement and daily technological changes, along with the swift influx of information, it is crucial to effectively organize and conduct the analysis process using modern pedagogical and information technologies, as well as educational and didactic tools. The process of gradually transforming the educational content in teaching specialized subjects at law colleges is an important endeavor aimed at adapting the education system to modern requirements and providing students with practical, effective education.

In this process, along with theoretical knowledge, great attention is paid to practical skills, creative thinking, and problem-solving abilities. The incorporation of modern pedagogical methods, technologies, and societal requirements helps students acquire new opportunities and knowledge. It is important to determine to what extent the educational resources intended for teaching special disciplines (on the example of the special discipline "Criminal Law") correspond to the successful fulfillment of educational and upbringing tasks, and to express scientific opinions on their further improvement. The main goal of training

junior lawyers is not only to acquire the necessary knowledge, but also to develop their intellectual abilities, forming in them the skills of independent choice and decision-making. When teaching theoretical knowledge in the special subject "Criminal Law" based on experimental and innovative approaches, the educational material is prepared for the study of the new topic by posing problems on the topic, repeating previously learned knowledge, activating the facts that have passed through the student's memory. Clearly envisions the goals of setting pedagogical goals, selecting a problem corresponding to the topic, reviewing the studied definition, rules, and recalling mechanisms, and encourages independent thinking.

The experience of a number of leading international universities shows that the introduction of new pedagogical technologies and innovative approaches into the educational process significantly increases the effectiveness of education. For example, advanced educational models and methods used in the USA, Germany, Japan, and other developed countries are aimed at developing theoretical knowledge along with practical skills in the educational process. Interactive learning tools, distance learning platforms, and multimedia teaching aids actively used in these countries allow for more effective and modern adaptation of the educational process.

The use of innovative tools plays an important role in the process of implementing international experience. In leading educational institutions of the world, interactive teaching methods are widely used in the educational process. For example, such methods as the case method, simulation, multi-layer learning models, and collaborative learning have proven effective in international educational practice. These methods allow students to combine theoretical knowledge with practical exercises, develop the ability to solve various problems, as well as apply the acquired knowledge in life.

The effectiveness of the educational process can be increased through the implementation of international educational standards. At the same time, programs adapted to the international level of education, assessment and control mechanisms, and adherence to high standards at each stage of the educational process are of great importance. Currently, the widely used in the world models of distance and blended learning, that is, blended learning, allow students to continuously and quickly assimilate knowledge. Such approaches allow enriching the educational process with innovative technologies. For example, through such platforms as Coursera and EdX, it is possible to remotely use international courses and improve qualifications.

Preparing students for the demands of the international labor market by incorporating global practices into the national education system is a crucial task. Innovative educational tools and teaching models employed in various countries worldwide enable students to become familiar with international experiences and apply them in practice. This, in turn, helps young professionals become competitive in the global labor market. Personnel trained according to international standards in each professional field will successfully operate not only in national production processes but also in international enterprises.

Moreover, integrating the results of international research into the educational process is of great significance. Leading research centers and universities worldwide are conducting scientific studies aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of the educational process. For example, through educational programs such as STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics), it is possible to combine students' theoretical knowledge with exact sciences and develop practical skills. Additionally, innovative approaches are designed to strengthen

both the theoretical and practical training levels of students, ensuring their success in professional activities.

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